

THE STRUCTURE OF SURGICAL BOWEL DISEASES IN CHILDREN IN THE BUKHARA REGION

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According to cohort studies, IBD in children in 15% of cases begins before the age of 6 years, only 1% begins before the age of 1 year [2].

The increase in inflammatory bowel diseases in pediatrics and the aggressive course of Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis lead to the development of severe surgical complications of the underlying pathological process. Depending on the severity and duration of the disease in children with IBD, the surgical stage of treatment is necessary in 14% — 80% of patients [1].

The purpose of the study: to study the frequency and structure of surgical bowel diseases in children in the Bukhara region.

Materials and methods: A retrospective analysis of 867 medical records of children who received inpatient treatment at the Department of Pediatric Surgery of the Bukhara branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care from 2019 to 2022 for surgical diseases of the gastrointestinal tract was carried out.

Results and discussion.

The incidence structure of children with surgical inflammatory bowel diseases is 50.35. The analysis of the nosological structure showed a predominance of hospitalization of sick children with acute appendicitis - 1775 (62.2%), intestinal colic-792 (27.7%) and intestinal obstruction -157 (5.5%).

The analysis of the age structure showed the predominance of surgical bowel diseases in children aged 6 years and older.

In the distribution of patients by gender, boys prevailed – 59.0%, compared with girls - 41.0%.

In almost all studies, children with constipation had a higher prevalence of boys with constipation compared to girls. This may not be the result of a true difference in frequency, but because of the difference in seeking medical advice and treatment. It is well known that girls are potty trained earlier than boys due to faster maturation, which leads to an earlier ability to control bladder and bowel function.

The analysis of data by place of residence revealed the frequent hospitalization of children living in rural areas, which amounted to 74.6%, while urban ones accounted for -25.4%.

It is known that prolonged constipation without treatment can negatively affect the condition of the intestines and the body as a whole. Fecal retention, as well as straining during attempts to defecate, contribute to the development of hemorrhoids, colitis, paraproctitis, rectal prolapse, coprostasis, encopresis, secondary megacolon, general intoxication of the body.

Conclusion.

The rate of hospitalization of sick children with surgical inflammatory bowel diseases is 503.9 per 1000 children. The nosological structure is dominated by hospitalization of sick children with acute appendicitis - 1775 (62.2%), intestinal colic-792 (27.7%) and intestinal obstruction -157 (5.5%), especially boys (59%) at the predominant age of 6 years and older, living in rural areas - 74.6%.

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